

Ravenna Effect: The new inflationary capital and the lasting Weimar Effect

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Abstract

Some findings by researchers on new capitals touch on the subject of this research, such as Cagan's Weimar Effect and Wiener's Versailles Effect, but there were no studies in academia relating the new residential city of the national chief of state to the emergence and persistence of high prices, which, for all intents and purposes, constitutes the inflationary drive. The objective of this work is to establish this link: Changing the capital of the country does not produce major cultural changes nor does it affect the economic behavior of market agents, as long as the residence of the president of the Republic or the monarch is not installed in the new headquarters. However, the newly installed residence of the chief of state in a city without status of secular capital, of at least 125 years, leads to persistent economic crises, brought about by high prices, lasting more than a century, even if this change of residence is not made official by law. This is a fact that should have been seen at least two centuries ago, with the disaster of Versailles, but there is a great distance between something being evident and something being understood.

Introduction

Nations develop around their capitals and their borders are defined by the taxation of territories. As in a kind of usucaption from top to bottom, whoever taxes, appropriates. Although the territory limited by its borders is formed under the jurisdiction of a headquarter city, at some points in history leaders who are not very fond of courtly life decide to change the residence of the chief of state.

For almost all of those who make this type of decision, changing the capital is as simple and innocent as changing clothes, even if there is a "menu cost" involved.

For the population of the country, it is not important where the head works, or where he officially has his residence, but rather where he actually spends the night. This is what happened to Emperor Franz Joseph I of Austria, who officially resided in Vienna with Empress Sissi, but actually spent the night in another city. Before that, the French chief of state in the decades before the Revolution of 1789 spent the night in Versailles, not in Paris, without the capital having been officially transferred there at any point.

It is not common for researchers to take into account the role of the location of this chief of state's residence in the political disasters that followed. On the contrary, they investigate the aesthetic and festive side of the new capital, which is always imposed by power, while the economy slowly collapses. The causes of these disastrous consequences have always been sought in other spheres, not in the geographical one.

The objective of this work is to establish, in a conclusive manner, the link between the installation of the residence of the national chief of state in the new

capital, with the consequent abandonment of the capital that had been consolidated for centuries, and the development in the country of the inflationary drive (high prices), of the deterioration of the currency, amidst the growing contempt for other national symbols. Furthermore, the research seeks, empirically, to determine the time needed for the consolidation of a national capital, which is also the period needed for an abandoned capital to lose its status in the understanding of the population.

Literature review

No matter how exhaustive the search for written material, there are, to date, no academic publications relating the rise in inflation to the change in the country's capital or the capital of the monetary community. It is easy to find research that attributes high inflation to construction costs, without realizing that the problem exists when the construction is of a new headquarters for the residence of the chief of state, and not when a city is built for another purpose. Nkomazana and Niyimbanira (2014), for example, point to the hyperinflation in Zimbabwe not due to the construction of the Borrowdale Brooke administrative complex, but to the issuance of currency for compensation payments and other costs, which are ultimately expenses.

However, it is important to take as a basis the writings that describe the political and economic situation of these cities chosen as the new residence of their monarchs or presidents, in addition to research on inflation.

Richard (1988), in his book *The Weimar Republic (1919-1933)*, describes daily life in the city that was the capital of Germany shortly after the abolition of the monarchy at the end of World War I. From 1919 to 1923, Germany was governed by the Constitution drawn up in the city of Weimar, where President Friedrich Ebert moved to stay away from the revolutionary upheavals in Berlin, represented by groups committed to establishing the dictatorship of the proletariat, confronted by their opponents, who were the counterrevolutionary militias. In 1923, an anti-inflationary plan involving the currency exchange was implemented by banker Hjalmar Schacht, which put an end to hyperinflation, but did not cure the country of its hunger for high prices, which only happened when President Hindenburg moved to Berlin in 1925. The name Weimar Republic was kept because the legislation was that of the first republican Constitution, which was in force until Nazism changed the rules in 1933.

Herrin (2022), in the book *Ravenna: Capital of Empire, Crucible of Europe*, describes the decades in which the city was the capital of the then-decaying Roman Empire. As was customary, the idea of the book was to extol the role of that city during the times when it served as the capital of the Roman Empire, from the year 402 onwards, with the title already mentioning the importance of having established itself as a melting pot of Europe, mixing Goths and Latins. Emperor Honorius, who transferred the imperial residence to the city, went down in history as a fool, but the city, in the eyes of those who analyze the period, was not the

source of any major negative events, even incorporating into its history the central episode of the Fall of the Roman Empire, in the year 476, with the invasion of Odoacer and the overthrow of Emperor Romulus Augustulus, in his adolescence. The Italian peninsula, however, was not in a good situation, experiencing frequent wars and overwhelming shortage. The arrival of Odoacer was greeted with applause and street parties, just as happened with Cyrus II when he took Babylon.

Nolhac (1898), in the book *Le Chateau de Versailles sous Louis XV: recherches sur l'histoire de la cour*, describes how Versailles, created during the reign of Louis XIV, developed throughout the reign of Louis XV. As always, the aim was to talk about the glamorous side of the new court, with detailed explanations of the rooms, such as "Madame de Pompadour's apartment" and "Madame du Barry's apartment". The construction of this château as a summer palace was one of the great decisions of Jean-Baptiste Colbert, Louis XIV's finance minister. Construction took place from 1631 to 1634 and, little by little, the place began to attract courtiers and replace Paris as the seat of the kingdom. The situation was thus consolidated until, on October 5, 1789, three months after the Storming of the Bastille, the Women's March on Versailles, motivated by terrible shortages in the open-air markets and shops, dragged the monarch Louis XVI from his rooms and, carrying him on their shoulders, installed him in the Louvre, in Paris, together with his wife Marie Antoinette (the women unconsciously knew that the crux of the problem was the king's stay outside Paris). The revolutionaries had ordered him not to leave the place, but, fearing that they would face the fate of other figures from the Ancien Régime who were being guillotined, the couple decided to flee, being captured in Varennes and later executed in Place de la Concorde on January 21, 1793.

Roux (1992), in the book *Ancient Iraq*, tells the history and prehistory of Mesopotamia up to the present day, including the fall of the Babylonian Empire in 539 BC. Ten years before this outcome for Babylon, Nabonidus, a Turkish soldier who became monarch as the husband of Queen Nitocris, daughter of Nebuchadnezzar II, left Babylon under the care of his son Belshazzar and went to live in the city of Teima. Under much pressure, he returned to the old capital in 539 BC, but was not well received, given the revolt that was taking over the city. According to Herodotus, he fled, but according to Xenophon, he was executed. Cyrus II of Persia, who was passing through the region after one of his conquests, was convinced by Babylonian authorities to incorporate the empire into his own. Thus fell the First Empire of Nebuchadnezzar's dream, interpreted by the prophet Daniel, according to Jewish history.

Heckel (2020), in the book *In the Path of Conquest: Resistance to Alexander the Great*, tells in chapter 10 how Emperor Darius III of Persia fell before the army of Alexander the Great. The city of Persepolis had been built in periods prior to that of this last emperor, but Darius III was the first monarch to reside in the city. With the empire that Cyrus II had built up, and which now extended as far as Egypt, now weakened, the young Alexander had little difficulty

in conquering it in 330 BC. This was the second empire to fall, of the four interpreted by Daniel.

Schiff (2011), in the book *Cleopatra, a Life*, tells in detail the story of the last occupant of the throne of the Ptolemaic dynasty, Cleopatra VII. When Alexander the Great died in 323 BC, after having unified the Old World around the Mediterranean Sea, without leaving an heir, his four trusted generals, Ptolemy, Cassander, Antigonus and Seleucus, divided the entire conquered area into four kingdoms. Cassander came to rule Macedonia, Antigonus Asia, Seleucus Syria, and Ptolemy Egypt, from the new capital Alexandria. The impossibility of reaching an agreement, which led to the division of the empire, indicates that the capital created by Alexander, Alexandria, had its setbacks. In any case, it consolidated itself and ruled an empire that lasted three centuries. When Ptolemy XII died, he left Ptolemy XIII and Cleopatra as heirs to the throne. She was 18 years old, but her brother was only 12. Ptolemy XIII's guardians, knowing that he was just a child, tried to ensure that power was divided equally between the two heirs. At one point, they minted the empire's coins with Cleopatra's face on them, without the boy's. This was seen as proof that she was trying to reign alone. They staged a palace coup and Cleopatra managed to escape, finding refuge in Syria. Now, for the population, the queen, who was of legal age, was the de facto monarch, regardless of where she was. Outside the capital Alexandria, the effect became the same as Nabonidus' reign outside Babylon. Ptolemy XIII was unable to be recognized as the sole emperor, as he had wanted. The empire began to dissolve. Cleopatra allied herself with the leaders of Rome in an attempt to regain the throne. One of the safest strategies would be to have a son with Julius Caesar, and from this came the boy Caesarion. Whether with Julius or Mark Antony, Caesarion would be the continuation of the Ptolemaic Empire. The calculation did not work out because Augustus Caesar, who replaced Julius Caesar when he was assassinated, declared himself emperor and ordered Caesarion to be assassinated. The Third Empire of Nebuchadnezzar's dream disappeared there. The Fourth Empire was that of Rome.

Methods

It is frightening that academia has not yet carried out the obvious verification that this research presents, since there is no need to go back in time and analyze cases from centuries past. All we need to do is look at the 20th century and the beginning of the 21st century. Why is this so difficult? One of the reasons is that people have little experience with long-term interrelations. This is why they attribute the emergence of inflationary impulses to government spending, something that is immediate and commonplace. If a person contracts the flu virus, the first symptoms appear the next day, so it was easy to establish the connection between the occurrences. If the virus had remained incubated for six months or more until the first manifestation, there would have been a very long way to go before the link was deciphered.

The confirmation of the hypotheses in this work is not done through statistical experimentation, once this is exploratory research with a qualitative approach. The path chosen here is to compare papers, facts and dates, and identify patterns. The experimentum crucis occurs by applying the concept to situations that previously did not seem to fit into it and finding that they were always waiting for a magnifying glass to show that they were consistent with the theoretical framework developed.

This was initially the case with the transfer of the seat of the Roman Empire to Ravenna. The original references were related to the most notable historical facts, such as the role of Versailles in the French Revolution and that of Weimar in the German hyperinflation after World War I. For Versailles, everything was limited to the alleged mismanagement of the Ancien Régime. For the Weimar Republic, the blame fell on the heavy burdens that Germany had to fulfill after being defeated in the World War. There is no link between the two facts, except for the residence of the chief of state in a capital that had not been consolidated for centuries. Empirical verification is that the consolidation period, if the country insists on the new capital, takes 125 years.

Regarding Ravenna, not any General History book details this event. For almost everyone, the Fall of the Roman Empire occurred with Rome in command, which leads to the understanding that the city of Rome continued to be the seat of the Western empire. And that was not the case. During a lecture, it was said: When Rome fell, the emperor did not reside in Rome. This was later found out. Romulus Augustulus resided in Ravenna.

Later, the application of the construct was confirmed in the reason for the outbreak of World War I. For historians, who are not obliged to be social psychologists, the trigger was the assassination of the heir to the Austro-Hungarian throne, Franz Ferdinand, when he was visiting Sarajevo. Gavrilo Prinkip, the activist who shot the heir, belonged to a group that fought for the independence of Bosnia and Herzegovina. The whole explanation ends there. But that is very little. The revolt that led the activist to the extreme act was fueled by galloping inflation that was punishing the empire. Now, inflation is produced by the issuance of currency, as Milton Friedman always stated. But the inflationary drive, the high cost of living, precedes the action of the Central Bank. In the paradigm of the helicopter that drops money on the island, developed by Friedman (1994), the first month of distribution of banknotes produces an improvement in the lives of the residents. Inflation occurs in the following months, with the repetition of the gift. As the fact is well known, only pathologically irresponsible economists would allow their rulers to create inflation by distributing money without return. In modern monetary theory (Armstrong and Mosler, 2020), post-Friedman, there is the inertial factor, in which the ruler issues currency to respond to demand, among other factors. And this demand comes from the inflationary drive, which is the persistence of the high cost of living. Therefore, the inflation of the Austro-Hungarian Empire did not come from childishness or monetary irresponsibility on the part of Emperor Franz Joseph I. The reasoning of the new residence of the chief of state applies. Confirmed. The emperor was

not faithful to Empress Sissi, as was well known. In his naive hypocrisy, he installed his mistress in another city, Bad Itzchl. There he spent the night with the dancer, no longer in Vienna. Bad Itzchl became the seat of the Austro-Hungarian Empire, in practice, but never officially. For the population, the official seat means nothing, except for a cover-up. What matters is where the leader actually spends the night. And if this place is outside the consolidated capital, then there will be a shortage of goods, with restrictions on products and rising prices, as can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1 – Empty shelves foreshadowing a shortage

Source: Free image from the internet

Results and discussion

This is an explanation of the Weimar Effect, which Philip David Cagan identified as the general impoverishment of the country caused by hyperinflation, but he did not decipher the source of the problem: (1) The role of capitals has always been neglected; (2) everything happens within the context of the abandonment of the capital that has been consolidated for centuries (Paris, Berlin, Rio, Lagos), which causes economic crises for 12 decades; (3) the abandoned capital does not only bring crises to the country, but to its neighbors who are culturally influenced by that country (Versailles Effect, Malcolm H. Wiener); (4) it does not matter where the government ministers are, but the place where the chief of state resides is vital for the country.

The most compelling historical examples of the phenomenon of the abandoned capital are those that follow, including some already discussed above. (I) Aton, who disowned Thebes, by Amenhotep IV (1353 BC), until its restoration by his son Tutankhamun; (II) Teima, who disowned Babylon, by Nabonidus (549 BC), until the incorporation of the empire by Cyrus II of Persia in 539 BC and the death of Nabonidus; (III) Persepolis, who disowned Susa, by

Darius III, until the latter was defeated by Alexander the Great in 331 BC; (IV) Syria (some region), which sheltered Cleopatra, the queen (50 BC), who was overthrown in Alexandria by her 12-year-old brother, Ptolemy XIII, causing the end of the Hellenic Empire; (V) Ravenna, who disowned Rome (402 AD), until the barbarian Odoacer took Rome, applauded in the streets, in 476; (VI) Versailles, which disowned Paris (1682), by Louis XIV (under the influence of the head of the French treasury, Colbert), until the Women's March in 1789; (VII) Weimar, which disowned Berlin, by President Friedrich Ebert (1919), in the face of workers' revolutions, until the restoration of Berlin by Hindenburg in 1925; (VIII) Abuja, which disowned Lagos (1991), by Ibrahim Babangida, with misfortunes still ongoing; (IX) Naypyidaw, which disowned Yangon (2002), by Than Shwe, with misfortunes still ongoing; (X) Borrowdale Brooke, which disowned Harare, by Robert Mugabe (2006); (XI) Nusantara, which disowned Jakarta, by Joko Widodo (2024), a president at the end of his term, with misfortunes yet to come (Subianto will take the blame).

Three important capitals of today, which rejected the previous one, bravely resisted 12 decades of setbacks until consolidation, but this happened at the cost of much loss of territory and naval power (Madrid, against Toledo, 1561), much blood (Washington-DC, against Philadelphia, 1800) and much diaspora (Tokyo, against Kyoto, 1869). A common fact for these three capitals was the period of great deflation at the time of the 125th anniversary of their establishment. In the case of the United States, the crisis was exceptional, leading to repercussions around the world, as was the case with the Revolution of 1930 in Brazil, the elimination of economic liberalism in Italian fascism and the rise of Nazism in Germany.

An example of how what matters is the residence of the leader and not the rest of the administration was what happened in Germany after World War II. With the division of the city of Berlin into a pro-Soviet area and a pro-Western area, the government was installed in the city of Bonn, which had no secular status as the national capital. There was no inflationary drive in the following decades, and this occurred because the president's residence, unlike what was done in 1919, did not leave Berlin (the fact that there was no inflation was treated as the "Berlin enigma", deciphered by the realization that it is not the location of the government that counts in the inflationary impulse, but the residence of the chief of state). As this is a pattern, when the administrative city of New Delhi, in India, was installed, there should have been a long period of inflation, but this did not occur, because the president of the country, unlike the prime minister, always resided in Delhi, the old capital.

Another phenomenon that should not be ignored is that configured in the concept of the Versailles Effect (Wiener, 2016), according to which new capitals that stand out regionally influence neighboring countries in terms of customs, arts and other behaviors. Historian Malcolm H. Wiener, the author of the idea, was the one who came closest to understanding the phenomenon of the Ravenna Effect (Marques, 2018). By applying the Versailles Effect to the study of inflationary behavior, it is understood why neighboring countries that are smaller follow the

one that changed its capital in the vicissitudes of high prices and inflationary impulses. Figure 2 shows what happens to the inflated currency in the new capital of the regionally influential country.

Figure 2 – The new capital causing currency devaluation

Source: Image generated by the author using AI

The economic disaster of the new capital can lead to a good result when one wants to destroy a bad regime. This is how the collaborationist Vichy regime encouraged the French in the mother country and in the colonies to fight against Nazism. Beauguitte (2010) discusses the scarcity and material poverty that hindered the work of French geographers at the time. Shortages and high prices are all the groundwork for an inflationary outbreak. Since the economy was almost entirely run by the German government, and the Vichy regime lasted only four years, under the iron hand of Marshal Pétain, there was no hyperinflation, but the French displeasure with the scarcity strengthened the ranks of the resistance. It should not be forgotten that Nazism was very strong militarily and that, on D-Day alone, the Germans shot down more than 900 British and Allied planes.

Conclusion

In August 2024, Indonesia inaugurated its new capital, Nusantara, abandoning Jakarta. The painful example of Naypyidaw, also in Asia, taught Indonesians nothing, because all the political and economic problems that have been occurring are attributed to fanciful causes, never to the real cause. Since there is already a lot of knowledge in the 21st century about how to control

inflation, there is the possibility that Indonesia will live with serious high prices, but without falling into a foolish inflationary regime - this is what happens with Nigeria, which installed its new capital, Abuja, in 1991, and faces a high rate of inflation, but not hyperinflation. For Indonesia, control means that the thermometer will have more difficulty measuring the fever, which will necessarily be present.

And just as happened with Jakarta, other consolidated capitals may be abandoned, if the explanation of the Weimar Effect, as presented in this work, is not incorporated into academia. On the positive side, new inflationary capitals that have been functioning as administrative headquarters can continue to play this role and solve the problem by simply returning the presidential residence to the traditional capital, as is the case in Nigeria, which can reinstall the chief of state's residence in Lagos. Then, to get around the problem of inertial inflation, it is enough to establish a new currency, with a new name and fixed value, as experience has shown. Possible counterexamples refuting these results will be welcome, because they will certainly, if they exist and are consistent, help in the development of the social science of administration.

Future research

It is necessary to monitor, record and analyze the economic developments of the coming years in those countries that have decided to establish new headquarters for their chiefs of state, notably Nigeria, Zimbabwe, Myanmar and Indonesia. At the same time, it is necessary to study what is happening to the economies of the smaller neighbors of these countries. Academia also needs to address what happens to the high cost of living in a country that gives up its new capital or becomes part of a monetary union with headquarters in a consolidated capital of 125 years or more.

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